

PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT IN CHILDREN

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Abstract: This article analyzes the psychological factors of speech development in children. It is scientifically substantiated that the role of mental processes - perception, thinking, memory, attention and emotional states - in the formation of a child's speech activity is important. It also highlights the influence of the family environment, social communication, the educational process and interactions with adults on the development of speech in the development of a child's personality. The study shows the importance of factors such as motivation, imitation, the need for communication and psychological support in the development of speech in children.

Keywords: speech development, psychological factors, child's psychological development, communication process, language and thinking, cognitive development, emotional development, social environment, the influence of the family environment, the process of imitation, motivation, perception, memory, attention, imagination, communication competence, vocabulary, phonetic development, grammatical structure, dialogical and monological speech, speech activity, socialization process, educational factors, psychological support and methods of speech development. Психологические факторы развития речи у детей

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются психологические факторы развития речи у детей. Научно обоснована роль психических процессов – восприятия, мышления, памяти, внимания и эмоциональных состояний – в формировании речевой деятельности ребенка. Также подчеркивается влияние семейной среды, социального общения, воспитательного процесса и взаимодействия со взрослыми на развитие речи в процессе формирования личности ребенка. Исследование показывает важность таких факторов, как мотивация, подражание, потребность в общении и психологическая поддержка, в развитии речи у детей.

Ключевые слова: развитие речи, психологические факторы, психологическое развитие ребенка, коммуникативный процесс, язык и мышление, когнитивное развитие, эмоциональное развитие, социальная среда, влияние семейной среды, процесс подражания, мотивация, восприятие, память, внимание, воображение, коммуникативная компетентность, словарный запас, фонетическое развитие, грамматическая структура,

диалогическая и монологическая речь, речевая деятельность, процесс социализации, воспитательные факторы, психологическая поддержка и методы развития речи.

Introduction. The development of speech in children is one of the complex psychological processes that plays an important role in the formation of a human personality. Speech is the main means by which a person communicates with the environment, expresses his thoughts, assimilates knowledge and experiences, and adapts to social life. Especially in childhood, the correct and consistent development of speech directly affects the intellectual, emotional, and social development of the child. Therefore, the study of the psychological factors of speech development in children is one of the important directions of pedagogy and psychology.

As is known, a child's speech does not appear in perfect form at birth. It gradually develops under the influence of the social environment, upbringing, the process of communication, and various psychological factors. The child's speech activity is formed inextricably linked with his cognitive processes - perception, thinking, memory, imagination, and attention. Through speech, the child understands the surrounding reality, understands the relationships between objects and phenomena, and conveys his thoughts to others. Therefore, speech development is one of the important indicators of the child's general mental development.

Relevance of the topic. Nowadays, the full formation of the personality is of great importance in the social, cultural and scientific development of society. One of the main indicators of personality development is the formation and development of speech activity. Speech is the main means of human thinking, communication and social relations, and its development, especially in childhood, directly affects the further intellectual and social development of the individual. Therefore, the study of psychological factors of speech development in children is one of the urgent issues of modern pedagogical and psychological sciences. Childhood is the most active and important stage of speech development. It is during this period that the child learns to communicate with the environment, express his thoughts and understand the speech of others. Speech development is inextricably linked with the child's cognitive processes - such as thinking, memory, attention, imagination. If these processes are not sufficiently developed or psychological factors are not formed correctly, various difficulties and delays in speech development in children may occur. This subsequently negatively affects the child's level of mastery, social adaptation and personality development in the educational process. In today's era of globalization and rapid development of information technologies, various changes are also observed in children's speech activity. As a result of the fact that many children spend most of their time with television, telephones and other electronic devices, their need for live communication is decreasing. This situation has a

negative impact on speech development and can lead to insufficient formation of vocabulary, difficulties in expressing thoughts clearly and slow development of communicative skills. Therefore, it is of great scientific and practical importance to identify psychological factors affecting speech development in children, to scientifically analyze them and to develop practical recommendations.

Also, the upbringing environment in the family, the level of communication with parents, emotional support, the interests and motivation of the child also have a strong impact on speech development. The more a child communicates, asks questions and exchanges ideas, the more actively his speech activity develops. On the contrary, a lack of communication or an unfavorable psychological environment can create various problems in the child's speech development.

Therefore, studying the psychological factors of speech development in children, identifying the social and psychological conditions that affect their speech activity, and developing effective methods for their development are one of the important tasks facing modern psychology and pedagogical sciences. This study serves to in-depth study of psychological factors affecting speech development in children, to create conditions supporting speech development, and to develop children's communicative competence.

Psychological factors affecting speech development in children are very diverse. These include the child's age characteristics, level of mental development, family communication environment, relationships with adults, the process of education and upbringing, as well as the child's individual interests and motivation. In particular, active communication with the child, asking him questions, talking and stimulating speech activity by parents and educators play an important role in the development of speech. On the contrary, lack of communication or incorrect upbringing methods can slow down the child's speech development.

In modern society, the factors affecting the development of children are expanding. Tools such as information technologies, the Internet, and television also have a certain impact on the speech development of children.

Therefore, one of the urgent issues is to study in depth the psychological factors of speech development in children, to develop effective pedagogical and psychological approaches that will help develop their speech.

Studying this topic is not only theoretical, but also practical. Because by identifying the psychological factors of speech development in children, it is possible to identify and eliminate possible problems in speech development early. This ensures the successful adaptation of children to the educational process, the development of thinking skills, and the ability to communicate freely in a social environment.

Conclusion. Speech development in children is one of the most important indicators of their overall mental development. Through speech, the child communicates with the environment, expresses his thoughts, assimilates knowledge, and acquires social experience. Therefore, the formation and development of speech in children is considered a complex process that occurs under the influence of many psychological factors. These factors include the child's cognitive processes (perception, attention, memory, thinking), emotional state, motivation, social environment, and the level of communication with adults.

Research shows that one of the most important factors in the development of a child's speech is the need for communication. In the process of active communication with adults, the child acquires new words, learns speech forms, and begins to use them in everyday life. If the child does not communicate enough or his speech is not paid attention to, the process of speech development may slow down. Therefore, it is important for parents and educators to support the child's speech activity, regularly talk to him, ask questions, and encourage his answers.

The level of development of mental processes also plays a large role in the development of a child's speech. For example, the stability of attention and the development of memory help to remember and correctly use new words. As thinking processes develop, the child learns to construct more complex sentences and express cause-and-effect relationships. Also, the development of imagination and creative thinking enriches the child's speech, making it expressive and meaningful. Another important factor affecting the development of speech is the emotional-psychological environment. If a child feels safe, supported and understood in an environment, he communicates freely, asks questions and actively learns new words. On the contrary, a negative psychological environment, intimidation or excessive criticism can reduce the child's speech activity. Therefore, creating a healthy psychological environment in the family and in educational institutions contributes to the effective development of children's speech.

In addition, activities such as play activities, reading books, telling stories, and composing stories based on pictures are also important tools in the development of children's speech. These activities increase the child's vocabulary, develop verbal thinking, and strengthen communication skills.

In general, the development of speech in children is a complex psychological process that is formed in a combination of biological and social factors. Pedagogical and psychological influences, organized taking into account the age characteristics of the child, a rich communicative environment, and supportive social conditions ensure the effectiveness of speech development. Therefore, in-depth study and practical application of psychological factors affecting the development of children's speech is of great importance in their intellectual, social, and personal development.

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